

Landing over their head

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Abstract: Parachute landings are not drawing much attention from historians and memorialists. The widely recognized parachute landing fall (PLF) is traced back to WWII. But there are at least several decades of intense parachute activity before a landing procedure is given a name. How are landings carried out prior to PLF? What is the context? This investigation is an attempt at a clarification of PLF lineage. A diverse range of sources, including early technical manuals, eyewitness accounts, physical education treatises are used for the investigation. PLF is a blend of Amoros gymnastics with Judo tumbling. The technique is scripted in Britain, but the roots more probably stem from an unintended international cooperation. This research offers an expanded view of the too often ignored act of landing.

Keywords: Parachute, Parachute Landing Fall, Amoros, Tumbling

Introduction

There are many excellent accounts detailing the development of parachutes, from Garnerin's first descent in 1797, to recent world records, [1] [2] [3] [4] [5] [6] [7] [8] [9] [10] [11] [12] [13] [14] [15] [16] [17] [18] [19] [20] [21] [22] [23] [24] [25] [26]. However, one crucial aspect—landing—is overlooked in most reports, [27] [28]. Parachute landings receive surprisingly little attention in historical accounts. Even if the technical difficulty in meeting the ground is acknowledged on occasion, [29]. The World War II-era Parachute Landing Fall (PLF) stands as a milestone in parachuting history, yet parachute landings are routinely performed since Baldwin's time, nearly half a century earlier. No detailed account of the PLF origins is readily available. This paper addresses a gap in the history of aeronautics by examining pre-WWII parachute landing instructions, drawing on contemporary testimonies and technical publications.

Simplified physics of a parachute drop

A parachute drop is like a body in free fall. The major difference lies in the horizontal dimension of the body or drag area. A parachute is just a device for a massive increase in drag area. As a result, the terminal velocity is reduced to a level more tolerable for the human body when reaching the ground.

Fall rate at landing is often compared to the height needed to reach the fall rate as terminal velocity. And the height corresponding to a terminal velocity is mass independent. Given a fall rate and a naught speed as an initial condition, the height h is given by Equation 1, where v is the fall rate and g the gravitational constant. The height corresponding to typical landing fall rates are given by Table 1.

$$h = v^2 / (2g) \tag{1}$$

Table I: Correspondence of a terminal velocity to a height.

Fall Rate	2 (6.6)	4 (13.1)	5 (16.4)	6 (19.7)	m/s (ft/s)
Heigh	0.2 (0.7)	0.8 (2.7)	1.3 (4.2)	1.8 (6.0)	m (ft)

A steady fall rate of 5 m/s (16.4 ft/s) is equivalent to a fall from a height of 1.3 m (4.2 ft). And to state the obvious, a parachutist with a Fall Rate of 5 m/s at an altitude of 5 m (16.4 ft/s), reaches the ground in 1 second. In other words, a jump from 1.3 m (4.2 ft) leads to a terminal velocity of 5 m/s (16.4 ft/s) at landing.

Classical mechanics views parachute landing as an inelastic collision between a body and a surface. Before landing, a parachute possesses energy described by $E = \frac{1}{2}Mv^2$, where M is the total mass and v the fall rate. After landing, the kinetic energy is zero and the momentum is transferred to the surroundings. Thus, a landing dissipates an energy corresponding to $(\frac{1}{2}Mv^2)$. If the Landing energy exceeds what the human body can tolerate, injury occurs, [30]. Thus, the main objective of a landing technique is to distribute the energy effectively to avoid self-injury.

Total mass and fall rate are key factors influencing terminal velocity. Factors such as the jumper's age, weight, skill level, and attire are integral to the parachute system itself. Environmental elements also play a role, including time of day, weather conditions, obstacles, and ground hardness, [29]. Finally, parachute landings are inherently brief and difficult to articulate, as they are rapid events marked by emotional intensity.

Historical sketch of parachute jumping

From Garnerin's first parachute descent to World War II, parachute activities can be roughly divided into five overlapping phases. Initially, parachute jumps are primarily a spectacle for entertainment. Then, parachutes serve as a crucial emergency device for WWI balloon observers in need of immediate evacuation. Next, parachutes become an essential escape tool for pilots in a highly dynamic environment. Finally, parachutes evolve into a strategic deployment vehicle for airborne units. Incidentally, parachutes are also adopted by specially trained firefighters, the smokejumpers, who use them for rapid deployment in remote wildfires, [31].

By WWI, parachutes are well-established contraptions for leaping from balloons, [19] [32] [33]. Parachutes used by balloonists are notably large and heavy. Early parachutes are probably 30-40 ft in diameter when laid flat, [23]. Garnerin's parachute weighs about 35 kg, [9]. And the burden of the weight is carried by the balloon.

Following WWI, parachute diameters follow the standard established by the Engineering Division of the U.S. Army Air Service at McCook airfield. Emergency parachute flat diameter is 24 ft, [15]. Training parachute flat diameter is 28 ft, [15]. And an additional frontal reserve flat diameter is 22 ft is mandatory for training jumps since late 1919, [15] [34]. The rationale for smaller diameter is lost amid the upheaval of higher-priority technological developments. In essence, the parachute is no longer carried by balloons. The new systems are designed for jumpers in need of mobility to carry on tasks unrelated to a jump. Most pilots do not experience emergency evacuation in flight.

The shift in carriers explains the delayed adoption of airplane parachutes. Deployment speed increases considerably materials stresses. During testing, balloon parachutes often fail, tearing apart when deployed from airplanes, [3]. Safety specifications become significantly more stringent, and development efforts focus on creating a device that is efficient, robust, simple, and cost-effective. Parachute systems transition from a handcrafted item to a mass-manufactured and regulated commercial product.

As airplanes bring new challenges, parachutes are the focus of discreet yet significant attention, [19] [35] [36] [37] [38] [39] [40] [41] [42] [43] [44] [45]. By early 1913 about 150 patents are in process or granted, [46]. Airplane, harness, materials, canopy shape and deployment are addressed. Annular, lobe, triangular, square, pulled down apex and with an equatorial skirt parachutes are competing, [47] [48] [49] [50] [51] [52] [53]. Size and cupola are diverse, [54] [55] [56] [57] [58]. In some designs, hoops are incorporated to regulate deployment. An alternate solution inserts a symmetric pattern of openings across the canopy to secure inflation, [56] [59] [60] [61]. In others, the canopy curvature is controlled with a line tied down to the apex as for Garnerin's parachute, [62] [63]. The Heinecke design pushes the line to apex concept further for a finer control of the fall rate and as a tool for a quick collapse of the canopy after landing, [43] [44]. The parachute harness sees a variety of designs before WWII, [7].

In 1919, McCook Field Type A parachute merges the best features of contemporary parachute, [1] [3] [4] [10] [12]. In the decades preceding WWII, Type A is progressively adopted across the world, including USSR, as the Irvin's parachute. Remarkably, four major McCook Field contributors venture separately into the parachute manufacturing business, achieving varying levels of success: Leslie Irvin with Type A, Floyd Smith with the Aerial Life Pack, James Russell with the Lobe parachute, and Edward Hoffman with the triangle parachute. The Irvin Airchute Company opens a factory in Britain in 1926, [10]. Gregory Quilter (GQ) is another successful British manufacturer of parachutes starting operation in 1932, [4] [5] [7].

According to Murphy (unrelated to Pvt. Murphy), US training schools progressively expand during the 1920s, [3]. But training is not standardized. No issues are reported with landing properly. Murphy's colorful account mentions 'the problem of landing' but it is not elaborated on, [3]. Apparently,

tense individuals present a high risk of injury at landing, [3] [64]. Tranum’s landing style is with legs loose, bent knees and slightly crouched. By contrast, Atherton’s style is with the legs tightly pressed, always pointing out, meeting the ground at an angle. Murphy’s landing instructions appear aligned with Tranum’s.

The development of airborne troops is initially constrained by the availability of large transport aircraft, [7]. Italy is the first country to deploy an airborne force in the late 1920s. Notably, Italian parachute systems rely on a static line mechanism for tighter control during deployment—a solution eventually adopted by most other nations, with early Soviet forces being a notable exception. Early Italian parachutes also employ an uncomfortable belt-style harness.

Building on the Italian initiative, the Soviet military develops airborne units on a massive scale in the early 1930s. Germany and France soon follow, engaging in various forms of cooperation with the Soviet Union. French instructors train in the USSR. However, mainstream French airborne program remains underfunded and is ultimately abandoned with the fall of France.

The United States, Britain, and Japan develop similar forces in earnest from 1940 onward, spurred by Nazi Germany’s brutal effectiveness in airborne warfare, [13] [14]. The British airborne program is created ex nihilo by a direct order of Winston Churchill on 22 June 1940. The Central Landing School opens soon after, at Ringway in Britain, [5]. Development is initially driven by domestic efforts, inspired by German methods, but later benefits from the Polish brigade resourcefulness, [5]. Irvin and GQ manufacturers play a pivotal role in the emergency development of wartime parachute systems in Britain, [10].

The US sets up the parachute school a Fort Benning as a training center for airborne troops. Training starts May 1940, [15]. PLF is introduced 12 June 1943, in the parachute school training program, [65]. According to Essex-Lopresti, PLF defining trait, namely feet and knee together is an import from Ringway, [29].

Figure 1: Pvt. Murphy’s PLF. Copyright M. V. Baker. Used with permission. The modern procedure enumerates the successive point of contact during landing: Balls of the feet, side of calf, side of thigh, buttock, then ideally, back.

Modern PLF Technique

PLF entry position, from top to bottom, is chin against chest, eyes looking down, arm up, round back, knees and toes are in line of sight with frontal reserve edge, legs and knees are tight together. Ankle

lateral and medial malleolus tips are in contact, and feet are flat at an oblique angle relative to horizontal motion. Legs offer little resistance to landing. PLF is a standardized landing technique typically associated to WWII paratroopers and still in use around the world. A PLF engineering model is given in appendix I. And Mark V. Baker's Pvt. Murphy '5th point of performance: Land!' offers a valid emotional narrative, Figure 1, [66].

Gymnastic landscape

Contemporary sources are rather silent on landing techniques. Thus, a logical inference is to turn to the Physical Education of the time. Gymnastics textbooks are likely to provide insights into the jumper's preconceptions and techniques for landing. Afrancesado Francisco Amorós y Ondeano (1770–1848) is a leading figure in early XIX century gymnastics and in 1830 the author of a groundbreaking physical education textbook, [67]. Instructions for jumping into a trench are the following. 'Legs are kept together, and the ground is contacted toes first as shown in Figure 2, legs flex...' (translation of the author). Figure 3 is an illustration of a very similar jump technique from a later French manual, [68].

Pupils are instructed to stop breathing for the jump, inhaling at jump initiation and exhaling at landing. The education board advocates the upkeep of a soft landing-ground. Under no circumstances are jumps executed in cold weather. Individuals over 30, particularly the elderly, are excluded from practice jumps. WWI observers are also advised to hold breath until deployment. And the age limit for British paratrooper is set at 32-year-old. Both recommendations echo Amorós instructions.

Figure 2: Reproduction of Amorós's sketch of a gymnast's landing posture (1830). Legs are kept together and flexed to dissipate jumper's momentum.

Fig. 19.

Figure 3: Jump down and forward, gymnastic manual, 1880. The sketch artist might have got carried away when illustrating a jump into a depth close to the height of a middle schooler or high schooler.

A significant horizontal momentum is typical during a landing and proficiency in rollover must be covered as well. Jones lesson on roll-over is as follows in 1890, [69].

- Front Roll-Over: Separate the legs a little, let the body fall forward, the hands striking the mat first, then, the back of shoulders and along the back, and last, the feet. Bow the back well and drop the head forward when the body strikes the mat.
- Back Roll-Over: Separate the legs a little, (with) hands on top of shoulders, palms up. Bend the knees and fall back, letting the hips strike the mat first, then along the back, and last the shoulders and head...

The above technique details a straight rollover. But a PLF has a diagonal component which does not appear scripted in western gymnastics textbooks. One must look in the fall section of a Jujutsu manual for an introduction to breakfall techniques or ukemi, Figure 4, [70].

Fig. 4: Ukemi (Break-fall) exercise. The game of Ju-Jitsu, 1906. The dashed line delineates the shoulder to the opposite hip roll typical of PLF. A forward roll is depicted in the figure. PLF aims at a backward roll but the diagonal component is similar. PLF backward roll is humorously depicted in Figure 1.

A point of note is the divergence between jumping and rolling regarding the leg posture. The jump procedure keeps legs together and a roll keeps legs shoulder apart. The discrepancy is likely stemming from educator's mindset for the moves. Some elevation is required for jumping, but rolls are engaged at ground level. In other words, the momentum engaged in the ukemi fall is smaller than the momentum of a jump from some height. Legs are not at risk of major stress for the roll, and spread legs are not raising a red flag in gymnast's context.

No rollover appears documented prior to the rise [16] of airborne units. Multiple photographic evidence demonstrates paratroopers practicing rollovers, [71] [72] [73] [74]. Lord et al. acknowledge tumbling is an essential skill for paratroopers, [74]. Finally, the naval aviation manual on Tumbling gymnastics includes a chapter on parachute training, [73].

Unsurprisingly, roots for PLF are noticed in various pre-WWI textbooks. But standard gymnastics of the time does not provide a ready-made answer to high-momentum landing. A solution other than the Amoros technique has still to be learned pre-WWII. A member of the military or a sports enthusiast, well-versed in various forms of physical education, has likely combined elements from both traditions, knowingly or not.

Unconventional landings

In a controlled environment, parachuting is very safe, though perhaps pioneering days are a bit riskier, [29] [75]. Voluntary water landings are softer on the body, but the decision carries high risks of drowning, [17] [75]. At least Charles Baldwin (unrelated to T.S. Baldwin) relies on catchers for one of his landings, [76]. A jumper notoriously lands riding a horse, [77]. Setting aside ethical concerns about animal cruelty and assuming a properly sized parachute, the quadruped does help soften the landing. However, the horse's primary purpose is not to provide a cushioned landing.

Failure at deployment is an assured fatality. However, exceedingly rare strokes of luck are not unheard. Lapham lands in a soft marshland, Alan Magee on a glass roof, Nicholas Alkemade on pine trees and snow, [78] [79]. Recently, Joan Murray's survival is assigned to a mound of fire ants, [80]. Victoria Cilliers must thank a soft, newly ploughed field, [81]. Sylvia Boden is also unharmed, landing in a 97 km/h (60 mph) wind in a soft marsh, [41]. The common factor is the serendipitous occurrence of a 'soft' layer breaking the fall.

Parachutist's weight

Jumper's weight, fitness and age evolve over the decades following the balloon-parachute act. Pioneer parachutists are young athletic individuals. And more than one acrobat is a lightweight female such as Katharina Paulus, Dolly Shepherd, Tiny Broadwick and Phoebe Fairgrave Omlie to name a few, [8] [12] [17] [82]. Occasionally the jumper is underaged at the start of the career. Tiny Broadwick and Leslie Irvin are the case in point, [10] [17]. Penfold's parachute is specified for 150 avdp lbs (68 kg), [83]. And Bleriot's targets 165 lbs (75 kg), [84]. Garnerin weights 126 lbs (57 kg), Ors about 151 lbs (68 kg), [59] [9].

On occasion, heavier or older individuals jump, and in the early 1920s the fact gets attention. Alfred Baldwin Raper is aged 31 with a weight of more than 95 kg (210 lbs), [85]. Raper's jump parameters are recorded and the average fall rate is 15 ft/s (4.6 m/s). No mention is made of the landing. Blanquier senior's emergency jump at 55 years old is also reported with astonishment, [86]. In 1921, Blanquier has no prior training, but landing is fortunately uneventful. George Harris jumps a 32 ft (9.8 m) canopy to avoid 'knocking holes in the earth's crust' with his weight of 84 kg (185 lbs), [87].

Training parachute systems carry a 22 ft (6.7 m) reserve, [15]. And some procedures recommend jettisoning the reserve to lighten the load prior landing, [7] [88]. The frontal, or occasional side reserve must weigh about 12 lbs (5.4 kg). The gain in fall rate is marginal, and the procedure appears to be an unnecessary distraction, [89].

A typical US paratrooper kit would tally at a minimum of about 32 kg (70 lbs), including the parachute system, rifle with bayonet and life preserver, [90]. The weight of the rifle ammo is not taken into consideration. US FM 31-30 Fall Rate vs. Load chart enables a customization of the load to each paratrooper according to total weight, [90]. The field manual recommends a fall rate not exceeding 4.3 – 6.1 m/s (14 – 20 ft/s). Thus, the maximum weight of a paratrooper carrying the minimum kit is about 64 kg (141 lbs). The kit must be arranged such as not to impede landing or hurt the paratrooper. The median weight of British paratrooper is about 68 kg (150 lbs), [29]. WWII British paratroopers do not carry a reserve parachute, demonstrating command's confidence in the equipment, [7]. German paratroopers are lightly loaded to facilitate a forward roll.

In summary, the post-WWI period sees a shift in demographics. A larger number of older, heavier and less athletic individuals is using smaller canopy sizes. Additionally, paratroopers are likely carrying loads pushing the parachute system at the end range of a safe operation.

Parachute fall rate

Hampton reports reaching the ground 'under the most perfect quiet and pleasing gravity', [91]. Baldwin lets go his parachute a few feet above ground, [92]. According to Mouillard, landings are very soft, and anyone handles with ease a fall rate of 2 m/s (6.6 ft/s), [93]. The Aviation pocketbook reports no difficulty as well, in landing with a 28 ft (8.5 m) flat diameter Guardian Angel, [28].

Landings are occasionally compared to a motor bus going at moderate speed or a fast elevator strike, [41] [94]. Contact is felt with jolting force, [95]. Most often the fall rate is expressed as a jump from a wall. Heights vary from 1m to 3 m (4 ft to 10 ft), [34] [96] [97] [98] [99] [100] [101] [102]. Mazer's report suggests fall rates larger than 4 m/s lean on the hard, [43] [44]. There seems to be agreement on a fall rate of 5 m/s (16 ft/sec) as the cut off value for a safe landing, [103]. Some early aeronauts place the threshold higher at 6 – 6.7 m/s (19 – 22 ft/s), [104]. Orde-Lees indicates 9.1 m/s (30 ft/s) as the limit for landing without serious harm. FM 31-30 targets a fall rate range of 4.9 – 6 m/s (16-20 ft/s). The layperson has just to know any high momentum landing with speed larger than 3.5 m/s (11.5 ft/s) might feel brutal.

Engineering principles for parachute sizing are also documented as early as 1854, [105]. Richard's formula, for instance, yields a flying diameter of 24.4 ft (7.4 m) for a load of 100 kg (220.5 lbs) with a descent rate of 5.0 m/s (16.4 ft/s). By 1876, a fall rate of 2.5 m/s (9.2 ft/s) is reported for a load of 1 kg/m² (0.2 lb/ft²), [106]. For a total weight of 100 kg (220.5 lbs), a flying diameter of approximately 21 ft (6.4 m) is considered adequate at a descent rate of 5.0 m/s (16.4 ft/s), [107].

Wise reports also a flying diameter of 21 ft (6.1 m) as enough for a parachute, [108]. Applying Orde-Lees' ratio of 0.71, the corresponding flat diameter is calculated to be approximately 30 ft (9.1 m), [40] [42]. Following the First World War, standard flat diameters stabilize between 24 and 28 ft (7.3–8.5 m), reflecting also a reduction in weight after cars are no longer in use.

Some schools favor also the deployment of the reserve parachute for softening the landing with an expanded drag area, when controlled correctly, [7] [14] [88] [109]. And the jumper must actively keep both canopies together, [109]. The landing strategy is costly as additional repacking is required after the jump, and wear and tear compromise the reserve integrity.

Parachute harness

Early parachute harness designs have a great impact on landing techniques. To put it simply, there is no harness prior WWI, and acrobats use a ring, a sling rope or a trapeze bar, [5] [110]. Alfred Berry is still using a trapeze bar for his groundbreaking jump out of an airplane, [17]. Early WWI aerial observers still use a sling seat, and some improvise their own harnesses out of necessity, [5] [110]. Then several competing designs emerge in the following years. Type A offers the best harness, but obsolete belt designs are still used by European operators prior WWII, [7] [111] [112].

Two harness features interfere with landing. The first is the attachment of the suspension lines to the harness; the second is the design of the leg straps. Calthrop's Guardian Angel directs the suspension lines onto a single riser attached to the jumper's back. WWII German harnesses still follow this principle, despite its obsolescence by the time of adoption, [7]. The design choice has two main consequences. First, a relaxed jumper leans forward on landing, with contemporary photos showing jumpers contorting to maintain an upright position, [113] [114] [115]. German paratrooper landing technique remedies the situation by favoring a forward roll landing. And the paratrooper is actively trained in facing the forward direction, [6] [116]. Second, post-landing recourse against strong winds is limited. The issue drives the development of quick release systems. By 1937, the landing technique has adjusted to the realities of the field, and an issue of Life shows parachutists crawling on the ground before grabbing the lines, [117]. Early 1920s see also parachutes with a central line tied to the apex, for a fast canopy collapse after landing, [43] [118]. However, the concept is not maintained in later designs.

Figure 5: Simplified sketch of lower straps for several parachute harness designs. (a) French observer, WWI, split leg design. Jumper's weight distribution forces legs apart. (b) Irvin's 1920 design and US 1941 T4 design. The issue is circumvented with a strap sling seat and leg straps firmly secure the jumper on the seat. (c) Floyd Smith's harness in 1920. The sling rope seat is lacking; (d) Irvin's design in 1934; (e) British Statichute design in 1940. The leg issue is mitigated with strap routing. Harness complexity of designs (d) (e) aims at providing a safe quick release system.

The issue with leg straps is more subtle. In some designs, the jumper's upper body weight pulls legs apart, Figure 5. This issue receives no attention. A quick review of various harness designs reveals that while some models carry this flaw, others do not. Harness evolution over time suggests inventors make the problem go away quietly. Harness failures are rare events, but Murphy records a couple of them, [3].

Legs

Feet are the first point of contact at landing, [117]. Baldwin reports landing pretty well on his toes, [92]. Pointed toes are still in practice for ballon jumping during WWI, [119]. And about 50 years after Baldwin, experienced jumpers still try to land on their toes, according to Life, [117]. US paratrooper training also favors toes slightly pointed down with ball of the feet touching the ground before the heels, [120].

Landing on the ball of the foot is undoubtedly a great demonstration of Amoros technique. However, its usefulness for a proper parachute landing is questionable, given the descent rate and the fact that paratroopers wear thick boots.

Stasevich offers a unique theoretical investigation of landing, [30]. According to the model, the distance needed for landing momentum annihilation is the key factor for a comfortable landing. A momentum reduction over a short distance is typical of a brutal landing. Let's push Stasevich's argument

to the extreme to illuminate the point. All other parameters being equal, a parachutist with longer legs benefits from a softer landing when compared to one with shorter legs.

Stasevich focuses on optimizing leg length for landings, arguing that legs should act as proactive brakes during descent. To put this argument into context, consider a leg length of 1 meter (3.3 feet) and a fall rate of 5 m/s (16.4 ft/s). At this rate, the height of the legs would be traversed in just 0.2 seconds. While Stasevich's model is sound, the solution implementation appears challenging.

Footwear is also part of the first line of defense. Contemporary photographs show pioneers wearing high-laced boots, [8] [11]. U.S. military begins procuring specialized footwear as late as the early 1940s, [121]. Incidentally, the new boots quickly become a source of pride among paratroopers. And a quartermaster report indicates paratroopers keep their distinctive jump uniforms pristine for weekend leave, [121]. In effect, the training film confirms the quartermaster's observations, [120]. Paratroopers are tough—and they show it.

Emotional state of Parachutist

To say the least, a parachutist is under emotional duress from boarding to landing, [29] [95] [96] [122]. Training might have been sketchy during WWI, if one is to believe 'Antichute', [123]. Flight Lieutenant Soden is publicly very upfront about his feelings. Parachute jumping 'does more than scare me stiff, it scares me absolutely limp', [64]. Dixon relates a possibly apocryphal story about the Duke of Windsor, [2]. The Duke admits he does not know how to use a parachute and has no intention of learning.

Admissions of landing injuries are rare. Blanquier acknowledges landings are on rare occasions very soft, to the extent the jumper is left standing up, [30] [124]. However, young Blanquier cautions against a rigid upright landing, as it can result in a broken leg. Soden seems to blurt out 'If one jumps in earnest and only breaks a couple of legs or arms, one has no right to grumble', [64].

Two points of consequence are worth stressing. First the risk of injury is coupled to the emotional state of the jumper. Fear tenses the human body, thus introducing a severe disruption into a smooth execution of procedures, [125]. Murphy illustrates the point with the example of Jonah, [3]. The unfortunate parachutist manages to injure a limb every other jump. Interestingly, serial injuries are not a showstopper. In contrast, another student is immediately removed from the program when instructors recognize the individual's inability to manage time appropriately. To the concerned instructors, the deficiency makes the student an assured fatality, in a context where a second can make a difference between life and death.

On the other hand, 'Gas Bag' more dismissive attitude might stem from training jumps on large parachutes, from balloons, [126].

According to Mumma, no training is essential for emergency use of a parachute, [61]. In truth, parachute training can be wrapped up quickly. But the risk of injury is still high, [20]. A thorough program is already suggested during WWI, [119]. And WWII army's parachute qualification course extends over four weeks of intense conditioning, [29] [65] [74] [120]. While parachute training itself does not necessitate such an extended duration, repeated practice is the most effective way to mitigate unsafe reactions to an intimidating and fast-approaching landing. And the accumulated experience gives some clarity of mind prior to difficult landing. 'Quick thinking and a determined effort is necessary to make a correct and safe landing', Essex-Lopresti, [29].

Landing instructions

For clarity, sources on parachute instruction are broken down into several groups. The first group reviews technical manuals. The second group includes popular accounts such as articles for the masses, souvenir and memoir accounts. The last group is made by the information gathered via medical publication on parachute injuries.

Technical publications

The proliferation of parachute manuals follows the evolution of a highly specialized audience. The materials examined were published between 1917 and 1944. Unsurprisingly, the military is an

important contributor, [110] [127] [128] [129] [130] [131] [132]. Early manuals serve a short-lived generation of balloon-based parachutists, [110] [127]. Then, the McCook Field group issues the first manual for jumping from airplanes, [128]. From late 1920s onward, parachute manuals target civilian users, [31] [61] [102] [129] [133] [134] [135] [136] [137] [138] [139]. Eventually, parachute instruction is also incorporated into general piloting textbooks, [97] [140] [141]. A few key landing instructions are consistent across manuals, and a presence/absence matrix is provided in Appendix II.

Forward motion is preferred. Legs are bent at knee. Feet are not over 12 inch (0.3 m) apart. Sink in a loose position and roll if necessary. No stand-up landing is to be attempted. A pull up at landing is also frequently suggested.

In the 1930s, jumpers are also occasionally advised to sit in the harness with knees kept lower than hips. The jumper slides back into the seat keeping an overall upright posture. The rationale is not made explicit, the modern reader might guess the seating alignment makes the ride more comfortable and incidentally, the effort needed to maintain the legs and feet together is reduced.

WWI observers are equipped with a simple sling seat harness from which they free themselves at an altitude not higher than 500 ft, roughly about less than a minute prior contact. In windy days, landing is executed with a backward throw, legs up, so that the parachute pulls clear, if not yet released.

Facing the forward motion is achieved by two means. A straight prolonged pull on a single riser engages a slow rotation after a short delay. The move requires some effort. Body twisting at landing is discouraged, [128] [140]. But by 1944 a simple effortless trick achieves the same result faster: Cross riser to create a line twist. The first option rotates the parachute with the jumper, [128]. The second option rotates only the jumper, [132]. The trick seems to be an innovation from the polish brigade, [5].

A key instruction stands out in Mumma's manual: Keep knees and heels together. The instruction is not further elaborated but it is also found in Murphy's account, [3].

Testimonies

Baldwin offers a rare early testimony, [92]. Baldwin let go of the parachute and land either on his toes or carry on with flips and rolls. In high winds, the fall is on the side. Baldwin has also no inhibitions, leaving the relative safety of a slow descent by letting go a few feet above ground. Of note, the acrobat has about a fraction of second to appreciate the altitude. Nearby crowds or construction might be useful visual references. The side fall is also of interest as it is the first recorded hint of a roll. Flips are probably part of the show. Plain common sense suggests any rolls is difficult to synchronize with landing and of little use for softening a fast, straight down descent. Overall, Baldwin's testimony suggests a slow fall rate.

A few trends are apparent when reviewing later accounts. The first one is the complete lack of instructions, [2] [33] [142]. Case in point, 'How to Descend in a Parachute' does not offer any insight into landing. Most landing testimonies when available are vague. Wright's mentions a fall on hands and knees, [96]. There are also descriptions reminiscent of formal instruction, [96] [143].

Jumpers tuck their body, bend the knees and relax muscles, [41] [119] [124] [143]. A pull up on risers at landing contributes to softening the landing, [96]. Figure 6 reproduces a contemporary drawing of a parachutist landing, [144].

A few testimonies are standing out. Antarticus's training plan is the only testimony of knee turned out, [119]. Pearson is the first to have noted the importance of keeping the knee together in 1926, [145]. His testimony is significant, as Pearson appears as a parachute instructor. The recommendation is also found in Murphy's 'Parachute'. Purcell is also the first to report a roll over the shoulder, in 1930 [122].

Murphy's account suggests two schools for landing. Tranum's and Atherton. And leg position tells them apart. Tranum's method follows loosely Amoros's technique. Atherton's technique is compared to a baseball runner sliding to base, [3] [122]. Thus, the legs are facing forward, knees still slightly bent. An illustration of velocity vectors is needed for making sense of Atherton's strategy, Figure 7. More likely than not, Atherton is on a lightly loaded parachute with a slow fall rate landing on soft ground.

Figure 6: Simplified reproduction of G.H. Davis 1927 depiction of a British parachutist nearing the ground. Frontal reserve and background are omitted in the reproduction. The parachutist is lifting the body by grabbing risers prior to landing. A rounded posture is apparent with chin down, knee bent, pointed toes, and feet shoulder apart. Arms should be further back for a realistic representation of a landing posture under canopy (the parachutist as sketched would have swung forward, presenting the bottom to the ground). The original caption is: Easing the ‘bump’ on landing. Making a ‘pull up’ of the body just as the feet are about to touch the ground. A striking similarity is self-evident when comparing to Figure 1 top left panel. Drawings are about 65 years apart. Leg width is the major difference.

Figure 7: Landing velocity vectors. a) No wind landing. The total velocity vector is vertical, pointed to the ground. b) Landing in high winds, the total velocity vector has a significant horizontal component bringing back the feet under the body. In this configuration, the approach of pointing feet forward becomes valid. However, the vertical contribution needs to stay reasonable for not injuring the spine.

Purcell’s landing method is very unconventional and challenging to put back in context, [122]. The procedure is to bring up the knee as high as possible holding them with hand. The description suggests landing in a fetal posture, with the caveat the posture leaves the spine vulnerable to trauma. Miscommunication cannot be excluded. The instruction is very appropriate with a small fall rate, a very soft ground, and lethal high winds.

Key components from several testimonials are listed together in chronological order, Table III. Not all components are adopted long-term. For example, Antarcticus is the only source mentioning clenched teeth, and the practice of dropping the reserve appears to have been short-lived. However, side-by-side comparison highlights a quest for an improved landing method, Table II.

Table II: Key components of a landing found in testimonies

Year	1887	1917	1918	1920	1926	1926	1928	1928	1930
Author	Baldwin	Antarcticus	Neumann	Anon.	Wright	Pearson	Clark	Whitby (Murphy)	Purcell
Country	US	UK	Germany	UK	US	US	US	US	US
Components	Toes	Teeth closed Knees turned out	Knees bent	Drop reserve	Pull up	Knees together Body relaxed	Deploy Reserve	Slide	Roll over shoulder

The progress in compact cameras and photography makes available many pictures of parachute jumps. Prior 1920, most pictures are taken from distance and grainy. Some silhouettes appear consistent with Amoros’s technique, [19] [42] [146]. Other pictures show balloon jumpers close to the grounds with legs wide apart, [147] [148]. Most photographs taken after WWI are of better quality. Jumpers near the ground appear often with legs shoulders apart, [149].

Newsreels offer also insights into landings for the interwar period. Many views of parachutists landing with closed legs are found, British parachutists in 1929 with closed legs, Soviet in 1934, French in 1937, [150] [151] [152].

Thus, critical components of the PLF script are found disseminated in testimonies in the decades prior WWII. The fusion into PLF does not occur in the US. And not all of them migrate into instruction manuals.

Medical publications

Medical investigations offer unique snapshots into the development of PLF, [65] [29] [74] [153]. A first paper from Tobin from 1941 offers a preliminary survey of parachute injuries sustained over the previous year at the parachute school, [153]. Participants are instructed to land equally on the balls of the two feet. Legs are shoulder width apart, and the jumper falls in a forward in a roll. The procedure outlined matches contemporary instructions.

The second paper from Tobin is presented nearly 2 years later, at an annual meeting of Military Surgeons. A change of landing procedure from mid-1943 is disclosed. 'Feet are held together with ankles touching'. 'Upon contacting the ground, the jumper goes into a tumble rolling over the fleshy part of his forearm and thigh and over on his back'. Tobin reports a total injury rate of about 1%, [65] [74].

Essex-Lopresti's introduction states without ambiguity PLF is a British export to the US, [29]. The landing position of the body is relaxed with head forward, shoulder round elbows in and watching the ground, [29]. Feet and knees are together. One allows to roll on the outer side of the leg, thigh, buttocks and opposite shoulder. Noticeably, the direction of motion has become irrelevant. But forward strike with a face landing must be avoided. Essex-Lopresti offers the most detailed description of PLF, [29].

Discussion

The lack of attention given to landings is somewhat perplexing. This oversight may stem from a contemporary lack of interest in the subject. Or a perception the exercise is self-explaining. Landings encompass a wide range of brief experiences, making difficult the presentation of a coherent whole out of fragmented records. Additionally, observers might have sanitized some of the most brutal aspects of routine landings. Regardless, this work highlights a neglected chapter in the history of parachute landings.

Before WWI, successful parachutists are young and lightweight fit individuals using large parachutes lightly loaded with slow fall rates, lessening the need for a formal landing procedure. The professional landscape might have also provided the jumper with appropriate gymnastic training.

After World War I, the landscape shifts. The industry standard for parachutes are flat diameters of 24 ft (7.3 m) for emergency evacuations and 28 ft (8.5 m) for training jumps. While fall rates slower than 4 m/s (13.2 ft/s) are valued, they are no longer a primary objective. As a result, jumpers land at faster speeds, less comfortably. Parachutists take the abuse, as the human body withstands the impact. Injury rate appears still low. However, historical records indicate sustained efforts to mitigate these stresses. A variety of adjustments is very apparent for training jumps. A remedy is being sought at least for trainees. Many characteristic features of PLF are noticed in US interwar accounts, however, they are not the direct root of US PLF.

PLF technique emergence is not well documented. And some guesses must be made for the evidence to fit together. The technique appears rooted mostly in Amoros's academic gymnastics, with possibly some Jujutsu ukemi moves blended in. PLF as known today, is very distinctly a legacy of the scientific management used by the military. A procedure is designed, tested and statistically validated, [29] [65] [74].

A perplexing aspect of the early landing technique is the selective legacy of Amoros's method. Emphasis is placed on the feet and toes, whose usefulness is questionable, while the more critical instruction of keeping legs together is entirely omitted. This point might not be emphasized because it cannot be executed. Harness designs might be a hidden variable. Harness might not be used correctly, by design or lack of instruction, with the jumper not sitting enough on the sling seat.

Thus, a key instruction for a safe landing is keeping knees together. A review of accounts of the interwar period shows a lack of awareness. Pearson’s and Dixon’s instructions are a notable exception, [133] [145]. Possibly, leg safety is not as critical when lightly loaded canopies are used in a controlled environment. And limb injuries are probably dismissed as minor collateral damage after facing dramatic life-threatening events.

Leg awareness suddenly becomes prevalent across the world during the late 1930s. The era is indeed very peculiar. Several critical military cooperations take place in the late 20s and 30s. There is a German and Russian secret cooperation. And in 1935, France sends missions to USSR for airborne operation training. Leg awareness is well documented for the embryonic French airborne by late 1930s, [154]. Some newsreels suggest soviet airborne is landing feet together. Undocumented cross talks and intelligence gathering are probably a source of cross fertilization. Finally, warnings are issued late WWII against pre PLF landing technique, [65].

An attempt at charting PLF lineage is given in Figure 8. The USSR employed parachute designs modeled in part on the Irvin system. While direct evidence is limited, it is plausible that early Soviet instruction drew on foreign—possibly American—technical precedents. French military picked up the splinted leg technique from soviets, and it passed to the British, directly, via the poles or both. Instructors a Ringway benchmarked and further developed existing methods, either from legacy or intelligence gathering, with or without GQ, Irvin and polish brigade’s assistance. Finally, a scripted procedure is transferred back to the US.

Figure 8: Possible lineage of PLF. Mostly western gymnastic with a touch of Judo. However, the contribution of each participant prior to PLF fusion in Britain is undetermined. PLF is scripted in Britain after apparently an accidental international cooperation.

Execution of landing procedures under stress is particularly challenging and the military addresses the issue with investing in in-depth mass training using towers, physical education and candidate selection. Appearances are a parachutist landing technique is not really of importance until heavy jumpers come into play, out of the necessity of military needs. Tactically, US paratroopers are loaded with heavy gear. And a swift regrouping is essential for a successful assault. Jumpers must be back quickly on their feet, free of landing injuries. One obvious contingency solution is to make larger canopies, stressing the established supply chain, further increasing jumper load and slowing down the fall, but at the expense of the speed of execution. Instead, command tightens landing techniques for the newly formed airborne units.

Conclusion

From showmen to paratroopers, landing techniques have evolved. Unsurprisingly, traces of formal gymnastics are apparent. Components of PLF are also noted in pre-WWII testimonies but the fusion into the PLF script does not occur in the US. The PLF script is definitely a British innovation. Leg

posture is not emphasized until airborne units with a larger momentum (mass × fall rate) come into play. US paratrooper's PLF script appears as a transfer of British instructional methods in 1943. But the crystallization of landing a landing procedure into PLF appears to be a somewhat unintended international cooperation of uncertain origins. Scientific validation of the landing procedure by armed forces medical services is likewise well documented.

Appendix I: PLF engineering model

PLF entry position, from top to bottom, is chin against chest, eyes looking down, arm up, round back, knees and toes are in line of sight with frontal reserve edge, legs and knees are tight together. Ankle lateral and medial malleolus tips are in contact, and feet are flat at an oblique angle relative to motion, Figures 3 and 9. No matter the horizontal direction of travel, the parachutist will arrange to roll backward. Legs offer little resistance to landing. The position is inherited from forebearer who learned it the hard way. Each element is very well thought and addresses very specific aspects of body mechanics, Table III. Some minor differences between schools are also recognized, [155].

Table III: PLF function Breakdown Structure

Feet oblique angle	Engage body to present buttock to ground. Protects Coccyx.
Flat feet	Spread load, protects heels, toes, and ankles, [156]
Loose knee	Spare joints and spine.
Tight leg	Strength in numbers. Protects leg bones and joints
Side butt	Bruised buttocks are favored over broken bones.
Round back	Assist rocking and rolling, dampens momentum.
Chin against chest	Protects neck and head from trauma.
Arm up	Protects head, curbs parachute reflex, [157] [158].
Line of sight	Maintains efficient posture

An engineering model views legs as a spring, or an active damper, buttock as a cushion or passive damper and the back as a rocker, [159]. The head is lost to the rocker as dead weight. As jumpers, like any other humans, are fallible, a few deficiencies are common, Figure 9. A couple of reflexes can be triggered when reaching the ground. The jumper may extend the legs with the unfortunate result knees lock up. Other jumpers just lift their legs up prior to landing. Both reflexes disable the spring and expose the rocker to damage, [160]. Spread legs expose the spring to serious damage. A few desperate serial offenders resorted to tying legs together, [161]. The angled touchdown safeguards the spring from excessive compressive stress. Arm-up acts as a barrier protecting the head against concussions. Finally, with arms down, something's gotta to give and it is not going to be the ground. A jumper might have too much forward momentum for the arms and shoulders to handle, [157]. In definitive, embracing an innate rock and roll is essential to jumper's survival.

Figure 9: Paratrooper posture prior landing, jumper mechanical model, typical deficiencies at landing, namely, locked knees, leg up reflex and spread legs.

A PLF posture is prescriptive. The jumper takes his position at a safe altitude and waits for the landing for half a minute or so. There is time for a meditation on the unbearable lightness of being, enjoying the view from a unique vantage point while it lasts, reflecting on the respective merits of

Arizona and China's landing grounds, or praying. Notwithstanding winds, a paratrooper's trajectory is usually a straight line down. Round parachutes have been phased out from the sport for many good reasons. One of them is unnecessary landing injuries holding back sport jumper's progression, [162]. In short, PLF is an efficient landing technique when executed correctly in the proper configuration, which requires practice. It is not a magic card for getting out of trouble. But PLF can make the difference in the subtle nuance between eating dirt and biting the dust.

Appendix II: Landing Instruction Presence / Absence table,

Year	Country	Market	Title	Author	Back to the wind	Sitting	Pull Up	Watch Horizon	Knees bent	12 inch apart	No stand up	Fall Over	Comment	Reference
1917	UK	Military	Kite Balloon Training Manual	Anon.	-	-	-	-	Y	-	-	-	Released from sling, hold w/ Harms, if windy legs up,	[110]
1919	US	Military	Parachutes manual for Balloons	Anon.	-	-	-	-	Y	-	-	-	Also inside basket	[127]
1920	US	Military	Parachute Manual	Anon.	Y	-	-	-	Y	-	Y	Y		[128]
1927	Germany	Pilot	Flugpraxis	Gymnich	-	-	-	-	Y	-	-	-	No twisting at landing	[140]
1928	US	Civilian	Russell Lobe Parachute	Russell	-	-	-	-	Y	-	-	-		[102]
1929	US	Military	TM 2170-72 Parachute Rigger	Anon.	Y	-	-	Y	Y	Y	Y	-		[129]
1930	US	Civilian	Parachutes	Mumma	Y	-	Y	Y	-	-	Y	-	Knees and heels together, side slip for facing wind	[61]
1930	UK	Civilian	Parachutes for Airmen	Dixon	-	Y	Y	-	Y	-	Y	Y		[133]
1937	US	Civilian	Irvin Air Chutes	Irvin	-	-	-	-	Y	-	Y	Y		[137]
1938	US	Pilot	Your Wings	Jordanoff	Y	-	-	-	-	-	Y	Y		[141]
1939	US	Civilian	CAB 20	Anon.	Y	-	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y		[134]
1940	US	Pilot	General Aeronautics	Lusk	Y	-	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Similar to CAB 20	[97]
1941	US	Civilian	CAB 23	Anon.	Y	-	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Similar to CAB 20	[135]
1941	US	Military	TM 1-440 Parachute, ...	Anon.	Y	-	-	-	Y	-	Y	-	Not facing wind, Wind less than 10 mph	[130]
1942	US	Civilian	Parachutes	Fechet	Y	-	Y	Y	Y	-	Y	Y		[31]
1942	US	Civilian	Parachutes	Floyd-Smith	-	-	Y	-	Y	-	-	Y	Lean forward, backward relax and roll. Watch arms	[139]
1943	US	Military	Parachute Sense	Anon.	-	Y	Y	-	Y	-	Y	Y		[131]
1944	US	Civilian	Parachute Technician	Zweng	Y	Y	Y	-	Y	-	Y	Y	Clarifies sitting - No back landing - bend forward	[136]
1944	US	Military	Parachutes	Navy	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Lean forward, cross risers. Crawl on ground	[132]

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Notes on contributor

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